

THE EFFECTS OF ALLOY ELEMENTS ON THE TENSILE STRENGTH OF CARBON FIBER/ALUMINUM COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The primary work on the influences of alloy elements on Al/C wires was carried out. It was indicated that the different aluminum matrixes (LF6, LC4, LD2, LD10) had unfavourable influence on the tensile strength at room temperature. However, addition of alloy element titanium into matrix could improve the tensile strength at room temperature, and increase the critical temperature at which the tensile strength of composites begin to degrade.

INTRODUCTION

One of major barriers to develop the C/Al composites is excessive reaction between carbon fiber and aluminum matrix at elevated temperature. CVD Ti-B liquid metal infiltration method is an effective and wide used method to produce the C/Al composites [1]. Ti-B coating can improve the wettability between fiber and matrix with advantage. But it cannot protect the reaction between fiber and matrix at elevated temperature effectively [2-7]. The alloying to matrix could be one of useful ways to block the reaction, and improve the strength of composites [4,8,9,10,11]. In this paper, the influences of different matrixes on the tensile strength of C/Al composites were investigated. The influences of addition of titanium into matrix were also studied. The mechanisms of effects of titanium on the strength of composite wires were discussed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composite wires (approximately 0.5 mm in diameter) were produced with the CVD Ti-B coating method. The carbon fibers were high modulus fiber M40 and high strength fiber T300, respectively. The matrixes were pure aluminum, LF6, LC4, LD2, LD10 and Al-Ti respectively. The main compositions of these matrixes is listed in Table 1. The as-received composite wires were exposed up to 660°C for 30 min. in vacuum (10^{-2} torr).

Table 1. The composition of commercial aluminum alloys (wt.%)

	Cu	Mg	Mn	Ti	Zn	Si
LF6	-	5.8 - 6.8	0.5 - 0.8	0.02 - 0.10	-	-
LD2	0.2 - 0.6	0.45 - 0.9	0.15 - 0.35	-	-	0.5 - 1.2
LD10	3.9 - 4.8	0.4 - 0.8	0.4 - 1.0	-	-	0.6 - 1.2
Al-Ti	-	-	-	0.73	-	-

* Except Al-Ti, all data are taken from [12].

Then, tensile strength, fracture surfaces were measured. The length of specimens for tensile testing was 100 mm. The part of the specimens were exposed to 710°C for 15 min. in vacuum, and then the matrix was dissolved with the solution of HCl and fiber was leached out and dried. The fiber surfaces was observed with SEM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. The effects of different matrixes on the tensile strength

The tensile strength of composite wires with different aluminum matrixes is shown in Fig.1. It is obvious that the tensile strength of composite wires with alloy matrixes is lower than that with pure aluminum matrix and strength of composite wires decreases in following matrix order, LF6, LD2 and LD10. Then we could find that the decreasing tendency of tensile strength according to matrix is consistent with the increasing of matrix yield strength ($\sigma_{0.2}$) and decreasing of matrix elongation (δ). Strength and fracture elongation of several matrix alloys is listed in Table 2. It is suggested that there be some relationship between degradation of tensile strength of composites and lower plasticity of matrix caused by matrix alloying. The extreme mismatch

Table 2. Yield strength ($\sigma_{0.2}$) and elongation (δ) of aluminum alloys [12]

	Al	LF6	LD2	LD10
$\sigma_{0.2}$	3	16	28	38
δ (%)	35	20	16	10

in thermal expansion between fiber and matrix could produce high internal stresses during preparation of composites. But plastic flow of matrix could be able to relax stresses completely or partially [13,14]. Thus, the lower the plasticity, the less relaxation of thermal stress and the lower strength of composite wires. After exposed to 660°C for 30 min., tensile strength of composite wires decreased (Fig.1) and the morphology of fracture surfaces changed obviously, no fiber pull-out and smooth. Meanwhile, granular reaction products around fibers were found (Fig.2). It was suggested that the serious interfacial reaction occur at the interfaces.

II. The effects of addition of titanium into the aluminum matrix

The tensile strength of T300 and M40 reinforced composites is shown in Fig.3. It is very clear that strength of Al-Ti/T300 is higher than Al/T300. If we define a critical temperature at which the tensile strength begin decreasing, the raise of this temperature could be found in Fig.3(a) in the case of titanium adding (from 400°C to 530°C). The strength of Al/M40 increases at the initial stage and then decreases at about 460°C. The strength of Al-Ti/M40 has no change at initial stage and then decreases at about 550°C. It is evident that the critical temperature increases about 100°C, which is similar to the case for T300 reinforced composites. Because of difference of fiber volume fraction, we could not compare the strength between Al/M40 and Al-Ti/M40 directly. But, the ROM could be as a standard for comparison,

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_M (1 - V_f),$$

Since the strength of matrix is much lower than of fibers, for simplified σ_M is regarded as the ultimate strength of pure aluminum in our calculations. The σ_f is 185.8 kg/mm². Thus, we found the strength was more close to ROM for Al-Ti/M40 than Al/M40 (Fig.3,b). We know, closer to ROM, more effectively the constitutes act. On this basis, we could say the strength of composite wires benefited from Ti addition. The morphology of fracture surfaces of composite wires was also influenced due to the addition of titanium into matrix (Fig.4). The fracture surfaces show more brittle fracture character for Al/M40 than Al-Ti/M40. After exposed the specimens to 710°C, the surfaces of the fibers leached from the matrixes were observed under SEM. We found the obvious corrosion pits on the fiber surfaces (Fig.5), which was reported early [5] and was considered to be the results of serious reactions between fiber and matrix. The pits on fibers from Al/M40 seem to be deeper than that from Al-Ti/M40. Thus, we concluded that the reactions between fiber and matrix were weakened owing to the addition of titanium into matrix.

The possible mechanisms related to the titanium addition may be the raise of chemical potential and formation of TiC. Titanium diffuses from interface into matrix at certain temperature has shown in work of Harrigan [11]. It made us think that the reason of

Ti-B coating failing to block the excessive reactions might be the diffusing of titanium. Yet, the addition of titanium into matrix might increase the chemical potential in the matrix, which may prevent the diffusion of titanium from coating and make the coating act effectively. Certainly, more work must be carried out to certify this mechanism. Another mechanism, we considered, is formation of TiC layer at the interface, which might be a barrier to reaction. In light of formation energy of carbide, it is possible that TiC layer have priority to form at the interfaces over aluminum carbide and would hinder the excessive reaction between fiber and matrix, which would be of advantage for the properties of composites. The results of Kashin [15] encouraged us to think this mechanism more possible.

In short, the addition of titanium into matrix has evident effects on the tensile strength of composite wires and interfacial reactions between fiber and matrix. It is necessary for more detailed investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The alloys selected had no advantage to the tensile strength of composite wires at room temperature. The tensile strength of composite wires with alloys matrixes is lower than that with pure aluminum.
2. The addition of titanium into matrix could improve the tensile strength of composite wires at room temperature and increase the critical temperature at which strength begin to degrade. The reactions between fiber and matrix were weakened with certain extent.
3. Equitable selection of alloying elements for matrix may one of important ways to improve the properties of C/Al composites.

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Fig.1 The comparison of tensile strength of composite wires with different matrixes

Fig.2 Morphology of fracture surfaces after exposed to 660°C (3000X)

Fig.3 Tensile strength of T300 fiber (a) and M40 fiber (b) reinforced composite wires as a function of exposed temperature.

Fig.4 The morphology of fracture surfaces. (a) as-received; and (b) Al/M40, (c) Al-Ti/M40 after exposed to 660°C, (3000X)

Fig.5 Morphology of surfaces of fibers leached from (a) Al/M40 and (b) Al-Ti/M40 after exposed to 710°C.(3000 X).